

Synthesis of some New Disperse Dyes

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The uses of monoazo disperse dyes are well-documented¹. The present communication deals with the synthesis of a range of new disperse dyes for dyeing synthetic fibres. The methodology for the synthesis of the desired dyes involves diazotisation of 4-nitro-2,6-disubstituted-arylamines (**1**) to give diazo compounds which on coupling with tertiaryarylamines (**3**) produce disperse dyes (**4**)

The spectral data of the dyes are presented in Table 1. Since the coupling component in each dye is identical, the shift in λ_{\max} is due to the substituents in the benzene ring of the diazo component. Colour intensification effect of NO_2 group in position *para* to azo group is attributed to increasing polar character and its involvement in the resonance system. With the introduction of further negative substituents in the 4-nitrophenyl radical, e.g. in the 2- and 2,6-positions, an increasing bathochromic shift is apparent.

Experimental

M.ps were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. The value of λ_{\max} of each dye was determined in acetone/alcohol using Beckmann spectrophotometer.

TABLE I—VALUES OF λ_{\max} OF THE DYES

Compd	X	Y	λ_{\max} (nm)
a	H	H	482
b	NO_2	H	488
c	Cl	H	495
d	OCH_3	H	504
e	CN	H	512
f	Cl	Cl	520
g	Cl	CN	524
h	CN	CN	532

The diazo components (**1**) :

4-Nitroaniline (1a) : Commercially available sample was purified by dissolving in hot HCl, decolourising it with animal charcoal and basifying with ammonia. **2,4-Dinitroaniline (1b)** : A mixture of 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene (50 g, 0.25 mol) and aluminium acetate (18 g, 0.23 mol) was heated in an oil-bath for 6 h at 170°, during which time ammonia gas was passed at the rate of 4–5 bubbles per sec, (32 g), m.p. 176°. **2-Chloro-4-nitroaniline (1c)** : It was prepared by chlorination of nitroaniline in conc. HCl, m.p. 132°. **2-Methoxy-4-nitroaniline (1d)** : *N*-Acetyl-*o*-anisidine was nitrated at 25° with mixed acid (30% H_2SO_4 + 10% HNO_3 by weight) and the product was hydrolysed with dil. H_2SO_4 to yield two isomeric mono nitroderivatives (2-methoxy-4-nitroaniline and 2-methoxy-5-nitroaniline), the former being less basic than the latter separated during hydrolysis, m.p. 137°. **2-Cyano-4-nitroaniline (1e)** : CuCN (9.0 g, 0.1 mol) dissolved in pyridine (100 ml) was added to a mixture of 2-chloro-4-nitroaniline (17.25 g, 0.1 mol) and pyridine (60 ml). The pyridine was then distilled off and the residue was dissolved in hot water. On addition of strong ammonia solution, nitrile separated as pale yellow solid (11.5 g), m.p. 112°. **2,6-Dichloro-4-nitroaniline (1f)** : It was prepared from sulphanilamide by chlorinating it with conc. HCl in the presence of 30% H_2O_2 and heating 3,5-dichlorosulphanilamide with 70% H_2SO_4 followed by acetylation nitration with fuming nitric acid and hydrolysis (12 g), m.p. 154°. **2-Chloro-6-cyano-4-nitroaniline (1g)** : It was prepared by the action of Cu(I)CN-pyridine complex on 2,6-dichloro-4-nitroaniline (1 : 1), m.p. 132–34°. **2,6-Dicyano-4-nitroaniline (1h)** : A mixture of 2,6-dichloro-4-nitroaniline (0.05 mol) and pyridine (40 ml) was heated with Cu(I)CN (0.01 mol) in pyridine (80 ml) for 5 h. The

residue left was heated with 1 : 1 HCl and then cooled, when the base separated out, m.p. 124°.

Diazotisation of 4-nitro-2,6-disubstituted arylamine (2) : Nitrosyl sulphuric acid used for diazotisation was prepared by adding ice-cold conc. H₂SO₄ (*d* 1.84) to dry powdered sodium nitrate (3.5 g) with stirring below 10° at such a rate that no red fume was produced. To the clear solution of nitrosyl sulphuric acid, 4-nitro-2,6-disubstituted arylamine (9.2 g) was added with stirring until a faint smell of nitrite persisted. The reaction mixture was then poured on to a mixture of glacial acetic acid and enough ice and filtered to remove the little undissolved acid.

The coupling component (3) : *N*-β-Cyanoethyl-*N*-ethylaniline was prepared by cyanoethylation of *N*-ethylaniline hydrochloride with acrylonitrile in the presence of diethylaniline by usual procedure.

Coupling to synthesise disperse dye (4) : *N*-β-Cyanoethylaniline (8.7 g, 0.05 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of conc. sulphuric acid (5 ml) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and cooled in a freezing mixture. The solution was slowly added to the diazo solution and the temperature was kept below 5°. Coupling was carried out by adding sodium acetate solution at a slow rate at pH 4.5–5.0 for 5–6 h. On keeping the mixture overnight the dye separated out. It was filtered, washed with water and dried at room temperature.

All the dyes of this series were synthesised using above method. 4'-Dinitro-4-(*N*-β-cyanoethyl-*N*-ethylamino)-1,1'-azobenzene (**4-1a**), orange dye (9.9 g) (Found : C, 63.28; H, 5.04; N, 21.36. C₁₇H₁₇N₅O₂ requires : C, 63.15; H, 5.26; N, 21.67%). 2,4'-Dinitro-4-(*N*-β-cyanoethyl-*N*-ethylamino)-1,1'-azobenzene (**4-1b**), orange red dye (11.2 g),

decomposed on heating (Found : C, 55.24; H, 4.18; N, 22.60. C₁₇H₁₆N₆O₄ requires : C, 55.43; H, 4.34; N, 22.82%). 2'-Chloro-4'-nitro-4-(*N*-β-cyanoethyl-*N*-ethylamino)-1,1'-azobenzene (**4-1c**), scarlet dye (10.9 g) (Found : C, 56.84; H, 4.24, N, 19.29. C₁₇H₁₆N₅O₂Cl requires : C, 57.0; H, 4.47; N, 19.58%). 2'-Methoxy-4'-nitro-4-(*N*-β-cyanoethyl-*N*-ethylamino)-1,1'-azobenzene (**4-1d**), red dye, (10.59 g) (Found : C, 60.82; H, 5.12; N, 19.64. C₁₈H₁₉N₅O₃ requires : C, 61.19; H, 5.38; N, 19.83%). 2-Cyano-4'-nitro-(*N*-β-cyanoethyl-*N*-ethylamino)-1,1'-azobenzene (**4-1e**), purple dye, (10.6 g) (Found : C, 61.82; H, 4.48; N, 23.86. C₁₈H₁₆N₆O₂ requires : C, 60.02; H, 4.60; N, 24.14%). 2',6'-Dichloro-4'-nitro-4-(*N*-β-cyanoethyl-*N*-ethylamino)-1,1'-azobenzene (**4-1f**), purple dye, (12 g) (Found : C, 51.96, H, 3.56; N, 17.68. C₁₇H₁₅N₅O₂Cl₂ requires : C, 52.04; H, 32.82; N, 17.86%). 2'-Chloro-6'-cyano-4'-nitro-4-(*N*-β-cyanoethyl-*N*-ethylamino)-1,1'-azobenzene (**4-1g**), purple dye, (11.6 g) (Found : C, 56.28; H, 3.72; N, 21.78. C₁₈H₁₅N₆O₂Cl₂ requires : C, 56.47; H, 3.92; N, 21.96%). 2',6'-Dicyano-4'-nitro-4-(*N*-β-cyanoethyl-*N*-ethylamino)-1,1'-azobenzene (**4-1h**), purple dye (11.4 g) (Found : C, 61.22; H, 3.86; N, 25.98. C₁₉H₁₅N₇O₂ requires : C, 61.12; H, 4.02; N, 26.27%).

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References

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